

Javanese Food Traditions and Habits in the Colonial Period

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ABSTRACT

Food is not only to sustain life but also has a symbolic meaning related to social and religious functions. Food is a cultural representation that is translated into eating traditions and eating habits. Indonesia's culinary wealth cannot be separated from the influence of foreign countries such as Europe. The process of European cultural hegemony can be seen through the introduction of various foodstuffs, cooking utensils, and also government agencies such as household schools that offer many European standards. This study aims to describe the traditions and eating habits of the Javanese people during the colonial period. The research method used is a literature study, namely by looking at the various traditions and eating habits of the Javanese during the colonial period as outlined in several writings, including Serat Centhini, Serat Goenandriya, Serat Wilujengan, and others. The discussion found several traditions and eating habits of the Javanese during the colonial period, namely 1) Daily Family Food, 2) Traditions around social life and eating habits. Food traditions and habits have various expressions and carry out social functions as a reflection of personal and community behavior. The development of Javanese food traditions and habits during the Colonial Period was greatly influenced by their closeness to Europeans. Cakes, stews, and various cold drinks are some examples of foods that result from this influence.

Keywords: *culinary habits, eating tradition, javanese people*

1. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is unique in its culinary simplicity. With a very wide area, Indonesia has various types of culinary with various flavors. The culinary wisdom of the Indonesian people has grown along with the arrival of foreign nations such as India, China and Europe in the process of relations between nations that have been carried out for centuries. The cultural acculturation that occurred between Indonesia and several foreign nations took place without leaving the elements of the local genius of each nation [1].

One of the culinary varieties in Indonesia that are heavily influenced by foreign countries is Javanese culinary. The Javanese nation has long been confused with other foreign nations because of its strategic position as the center of economic activity in the archipelago. The culinary trail of Java can be traced through various historical sources such as Serat Centini, the Negarakertagama Book, travel reports (one of which is Justus van Maurik's travel report), household newspapers/magazines, kookboek, and so on. Writings on the history and culinary culture of Java are now easy to find. Fadly Rahman, Andreas Maryoto, Julie Sutardjana, Sri

Owen, and Suryatini N. Ganie are some of the names that have attracted attention in the culinary field.

Sri Owen in his book "Indonesian Regional Food & Cookery" (1999) not only writes various food recipes that exist in several regions in Indonesia but also describes various food processing habits and techniques that can be used in practicing these food recipes including several foods. Java. Fadly Rahman in his book "Rijsttafel: Indonesian Culinary Culture in the Colonial Period 1870-1942" (2011) discusses the eating habits of the Dutch East Indies in the upper class as seen in the rijsttafel culture with a Javanese background. . Andreas Maryoto in his book "Food Trails: History, Cross-Culture, and the Future" (2009) identifies various cross-cultural experiences experienced by Indonesians, one of which is in the culinary field. Suryatini N. Ganie in his book "Culinary Masterpieces: 5000 Recipes of Food and Beverages in Indonesia" not only writes various recipes of specialties in various regions in Indonesia but also writes various recipes that have been widely recognized by the public since the 1900s. Julie Sutardjana in her book "250 Legendary Recipes of 3 Selected Ages" wrote many popular food recipes in the Dutch East Indies since the 1900s.

In particular, the research that has been conducted has not yet addressed the development of Javanese eating habits which were widely recognized by the upper-middle class in Java during the colonial period, especially those who had been influenced by Europeans. This research will discuss the traditions and eating habits of middle-class Javanese people in the Dutch East Indies, especially those influenced by European culture. The 1901 Ethical Policy seemed to open access for the Javanese people to immerse themselves in European culture.

2. Research Methods

The research process is carried out by taking literature studies from literature, books, and the internet. Then conduct studies and studies that are relevant to the research. To discuss the research results, a description was carried out by linking from literature, books, and the internet. Then make conclusions about the research results that have been drawn under the objectives of this study.

3. Result and Discussion

3.1 Overview of Javanese Society in the Colonial Era

The arrival of Europeans in Indonesia in the 17th century was for trade, but in its development, they expanded their territory for colonial purposes. The expansion of territory could not only be done by the Europeans themselves, but they also needed local allies. But on the other hand, many local governments disliked the treatment of Europeans and put up a lot of resistance. After attacks by some local elites in Indonesia in the 19th century, the Dutch began to be careful about their colonial roots, especially in Java. The colonial regime took a more conservative approach. They compromised wherever possible with the local elite. This meant that the Dutch began to identify one by one local elite who were willing to work together, both in Java and in each of their new colonies in Indonesia [2].

The expansion of the territory carried out by the Dutch at that time had an impact on the social fabric of Indonesian society. The king was no longer the only supreme layer in the social structure of Indonesian society at that time. Western powers that came together with the slow growth of the Islamic empire have created Bumiputera government elites in almost all of Southeast Asia. This condition often makes the existing social hierarchy more rigid and

inflexible. Meanwhile, the social gap between the local elite and the community is getting bigger, even the two are enemies. Some opposed colonial intervention and resented these Bumiputera "allies". Social hierarchies often sparked bloody revenge when colonial power weakened or slowly disintegrated in the 20th century. These ethnic divisions were often reinforced by 'racial' differences that seemed to be used as a strategy by the colonial authorities to divide and define their colonies [2].

The cultural contacts made between Europeans and Bumiputera in the Dutch East Indies gradually gave rise to a new mixture. The mix of cultures or mixed cultures supported by a group of Dutch Indies is known as "Indies Culture" [3]. The development of Indies culture could not be separated from the influence of the women living in the Dutch East Indies, both Bumiputera and European women.

3.2 Strengthening European Cultural Hegemony on Javanese Culinary

The strengthening of European cultural hegemony towards Javanese culinary occurred in 1901-1942 through various channels. These routes include the introduction of foodstuffs and advances in transportation systems. Canned foods and foods such as butter, oil, and various flours were introduced through advertisements in women's newspapers/magazines as well as through various food recipes published in household newspaper columns. The transportation system that is increasingly advanced also helps this spreading process.

The introduction of cooking technology is also mostly done through columns in household newspapers. In these columns, many writings provide information about how to live a healthy life that can be done by processing food properly. Besides, Berkum [4] also offered a new standard for housewives through cooking utensils such as stoves, pots of various sizes, pans, water kettles, cutting boards, knives, various filters, marble countertops or pot racks, small knives, forks, spoons, bottle openers, egg beaters, spice crushers, plates and some bottles that can be used to store various kinds of spices. He also argued that it was necessary to make improvements to the family kitchens in the Dutch East Indies by taking into account the applicable standards in Europe, namely by using a chimney, sink, and a flat and clean floor (without holes and dust).

Most of the cooks/cooks from the upper-middle-class families in the Dutch East Indies were Bumiputera women. The skills of these cooks have always been prioritized by European housewives [5]. In the 1930s the European housewives' association organized cooking courses for the "European menu" for Bumiputera chefs [6]. On the other hand, the white mistress was also encouraged to be a role model for her servants. Through the book of life guidelines in the Dutch East Indies, women are expected to understand and have sympathy for their assistants to improve and elevate the conditions of their assistants [7]. The establishment of the Roemah Tangga School, whose teachers are European and Eurasian women, has encouraged many Bumiputera women from the middle class to follow the culinary habits of European society through learning. This is also encouraged by the increasing number of kookboek written as manuals for students in vocational schools. One of the kookboek is entitled *Het Nieuwe Kookboek* which is the writing of van der Meijden, JMJ. C. Strengthening European cultural hegemony was further strengthened by the establishment of slaughterhouses in several regions in the Dutch East Indies to ensure the values of health and hygiene for each animal feed.

3.3 Forms of European Cultural Influence on Javanese Culinary

Identification of the influence of European culture on Javanese culinary can be done through the variety of foods consumed by the Bumiputera community before the influence of European culture strengthened it. Joseph Banks (1770) in his travel report stated that the food served by the community in Batavia was very simple. Boiled rice was a major part of the diet of the Batavian people, both rich and poor, rice was always served with a small amount of fish, buffalo, or poultry, and sometimes served with the dried fish and shrimp known to the Chinese. Each food that is processed is inseparable from a large number of red chilies and seasonings. They also know various kinds of cakes made from rice flour. By their standards, the food he consumed was abundant. Islamic teachings prohibit these people from drinking alcoholic beverages [8].

The eating habits carried out by people in Java are different from the habits practiced by European people (the Netherlands). John Barrow (1792) in his report tells of a banquet held by the Dutch during a stopover in Batavia before continuing his journey to China. At a banquet, the Dutch in Batavia used to serve wine and gin, cordials (sweet wine), cakes, and sweets. This dish is always served before the meal begins. When the meal begins, the food served includes boiled or steamed fish, poultry cooked in curry along with rice noodles, turkey and capon chicken (capon), various meats (boiled, grilled, and cooked in broth), soup, pudding, and various kinds of cakes. dry. A slave stands behind a guest chair pouring Dutch or Danish wine, gin, liquor, and beer. Another custom that the Dutch practice at dinner parties is to ask themselves to take a nap before continuing with a larger meal [8].

In the 20th century, the culinary culture of the Dutch Indies community was very diverse. The racial grouping of the population at that time had an impact on the diet and habits of the Dutch Indies. Europeans deliberately create luxurious lifestyles to show their social status, including their eating culture. The specialty of their food can be seen from the number of dishes and aspects of the presentation that seem like a miniature colonial government. The arrival of European women, whose numbers increased around the 1900s, brought about a new change in the eating culture in the Indies with the awakening of the awareness of 'Western life' [9].

Emphasis on an exclusive dining culture with a variety of dishes at one dining table is commonly called rijsttafel by European families, especially the Dutch. The term rijsttafel was first used by the Dutch to denote the hereditary habit of eating rice which eventually became their own culture within the scope of Dutch life. Rijst itself means rice or rice, while Tafel, apart from the meaning table, also means decoration for cooking. The term rijsttafel came into use in Dutch families around the 1870s [9].

At first, the presentation of rijsttafel always involved many waiters circulating various types of dishes. Some typical Dutch menus that are suitable to be served in a rijsttafel dish include various vegetable soups, beef tongue, potato croquette, boiled asparagus, lobster with mayonnaise, salad, pudding, fruit, bread, various processed mushrooms, pickles, beef, poultry, chicken, potatoes, biscuits with cheese, red wine, coffee, tea and iced cherries.

The rijsttafel menu that can be served for vegetarians includes vegetable soup, potatoes with butter sauce, white beans with sour egg sauce, lettuce, cornstarch pudding with berry or tamarillo sauce, salad with french fries, eggs with mushrooms and lemon, tomato soup, peanuts, peas with mashed potatoes, macaroni with raisins, spinach with potatoes and cocoa butter, macaroni and cheese, potato soup, chocolate pudding with vanilla sauce, cabbage and potatoes boiled together with milk and butter, cornstarch pudding with pineapple sauce, scrambled eggs with tomatoes, salad (tomatoes, radishes, and eggs), macaroni soup, cakes, and fruits [4]. Meanwhile, Djoko Soekiman [3] states that the dishes commonly served in rijsttafel include soup rice, fried rice, gado-gado, rames rice, and spring rolls.

Popular menus favored by the Dutch East Indies in the 1900s included *zwartzuur*, hotspot, ham with soup, bread, tart, pudding, agar-agar (*goedir / gudir*), *freekedelen* (cake), *smoor* (stew), rolled, *soep* (soup), *biefstuk*, *resouilles*, various ice drinks (*es puter*), egg noodles, pilus, soy sauce grilled chicken, fried prawns, coffee milk, botok prawns, crab, chili sauce, *sayur lodeh* Semarang, rice kebuli, *sayur menir*, *sayur lodeh* Surabaya, *pindang* soy sauce, *besengek*, soy sauce pepper chicken, goat curry, pudding, omelet, chicken satay, meat satay, mutton satay, serundeng, and others.

The influence of European culture, in this case, is also seen in the presentation of certain foods such as rice kebuli, dawet, and sayur menir which were originally only found in a series of selamatan ceremonies. This shows a shift in the function of these foods. The food served in Indonesian submarine ceremonies has a certain meaning, so it can only be found at certain times. However, this situation is different from what happened in the Dutch East Indies in the 1900s, where the functional values of food were no longer seen only based on customary and religious values but were also more commercial in nature.

Another habit of the Dutch East Indies, especially the Javanese who was influenced by Europeans, is the habit of drinking ice water. Lombard [10] states that the habit of drinking cold drinks began to develop in the Dutch East Indies since the end of the 19th century when the method of making ammonia invented by Europeans was brought to Java in 1880. and experienced great success. In just ten years, ice factories proliferated in the major cities of the Dutch East Indies.

3.4 Daily Javanese Family Meals in the Colonial Era

Food is one of the necessities needed by every human being because in food there are calories that are very necessary for a person's body and mental growth so that their survival can be maintained. However, the need for food for everyone's daily needs is not the same, because it is determined by the natural conditions and the environmental conditions in which he lives. For example, there is an area where the soil and climate only allow corn and cassava (*palawija*) to be planted and cannot be planted with rice, so the people in that area make corn and cassava (*palawija*) as a staple food. Sometimes many people in the area think that they haven't eaten if they haven't eaten the staple food in the form of corn or cassava.

Food according to its type and function is classified into 4 parts, namely: 1) Staple food, 2) Side dishes, 3) Snack Food, 4) Snack Food.

3.4.1 Staple food

The staple food is a type of food that is a staple food ingredient containing carbohydrates because carbohydrates are filling and function to strengthen or increase energy. The staple food of the Javanese during the colonial period was food made from rice (rice, food made from cassava, food made from corn).

This staple food ingredient derived from rice is known to the public as rice [11]. The meaning of rice is rice cooked by cooking or steaming. Apart from Javanese rice which is on the slopes of the mountains where the soil conditions are not suitable for growing rice, most of them consume side crops, namely, feed on tubers.

3.4.2 Vegetable side dishes

Side dishes are food that is the result of the processing of a food ingredient, which is obtained from complex cooking, plantation products, fishery cooked from several ingredients

together. Community side dishes are the completeness of eating basic food. These side dishes are divided into three parts, namely vegetable, animal, and fruit side dishes.

This side dish in colonial times contained several European eating cultures, one of which was the *pergedel* side dish. The raw materials from Java at that time did not have to be potatoes from *kimpul*, taro, sweet potatoes seasoned with shallots, garlic, pepper, and salt. The material to be processed is peeled and cleaned, sliced. Jalu fried first and partially steamed and then mashed. The spices are mashed and made into a dough with ingredients that have been cooked and mashed. Make dots then dip them in the beaten egg, then fry them in oil that has been heated by cooking.

Apart from *pergedel*, the Javanese at that time also started cooking soup consisting of tang, carrots, cauliflower, peas, leeks, celery with garlic, pepper, and salt. All ingredients are cut according to taste. The spices are mashed and then sauteed with the prepared ingredients. Put the chicken/beef broth in the vegetable stir fry and cook until done.

3.4.3 Animal side dishes

What is meant by animal side dishes are side dishes that are usually processed from the results of livestock and fisheries businesses. Some are processed by themselves or can be purchased at the market, for example, Fried chicken, meat stew, pindang fish, chicken opor or endhog opor or chicken eggs, and others. In colonial times, animal side dishes were rarely consumed as a daily food for the lower classes. The lower-class people usually consume it when it is *slametan*.

3.4.4 Fruits

Fruits that come from plantation crops that are cultivated only in small or large areas, for example, avocado, star fruit, mango, durian, orange, papaya, jackfruit, banana, rambutan, salak, sapodilla, soursop, tomato, sugar apple. The fruit is there. which are consumed by themselves or sold to the market.

One of the popular fruits eaten during the colonial period was the mango. At that time, mangoes were mostly ripened in jars or baskets and given dry leaves. The goal is to cook quickly, then cover the basket or jar tightly. Apart from mangoes, it is not uncommon for Javanese people to also consume Tomatoes (*Rucuh*) which are flavored with sugar and a little water according to their taste. Tomatoes are selected which are tired of cooking and then washed clean, after peeling the skin first then cut into small pieces, given a little sugar. Put it in a glass or bowl, then eat with a spoon after stirring and lightly crushed. This fruit as a dessert after meals, especially suitable when the air is hot.

3.4.5 Beverage

During the colonial period, the Javanese used to consume various types of drinks, one of which was ginger, *wedang soklat*, *wedang* coffee, tea, and various other types of drinks.

One of the popular iced drinks at that time was iced tea. The process is quite simple: put hot water in a teapot or cup, then add the tea powder. After that, give sugar and tea can be drunk. Use sugar according to the taste you drink. If you prefer something sweeter, add more sugar or mix it with more tea water. When served, what if you like it can be added ice.

3.4.6 Snack

Complementary foods are foods that are processed and serve as staple snacks. The Javanese often refer to it as "*nyamikan*" or "*camilan*". It is usually served between before breakfast or

between breakfast and lunch, and between lunch and dinner: Boiled Tela, Labung-Limpung, Boiled Mlinjo, Boiled Corn, and so on.

3.4. 7 Snack Food

Snack food is food that is usually sold on the market, in restaurants in the form of snacks or snacks that can replace the main meal. For rural people, they usually buy these snacks at the market when they are going to sell basil. After their needs run out, they buy snacks to take home and enjoy with their family members. Another name for street food is Jajanan Pasar. Some snacks that can be found during the colonial period are: Tofu, which is tofu with a lot of content. The carrots and bean sprouts are initially cooked, then processed with flour dough seasoned with spices, tofu filled with carrots and bean sprouts that have been cooked beforehand then dipped in flour mixture, then fried. Besides knowing there are many kinds of street food, namely nagasari, flour fried tempeh, mendhut, klepon, slondok or alen-alen, tetel, gethuk watercress, etc.

3.5 Food at Traditional Javanese Ceremonies in the Colonial Era: A Case Study of Javanese Manuscripts.

Javanese manuscripts have various fillings, including traditional food. The manuscripts discussed in this paper, especially those containing traditional foods, namely *Serat Centhini*, *Serat Goenandrija*, *Serat Wilujengan*, *Jumenengan*, *Kraman*, *Mangkunegaran*, and *Primbun Lukmanakim Adammakna*.

Serat Centhini is a work of Paku Buwana V which is quite famous. *Serat Centhini* was written by Pangeran Adipati Anom long before he served as king of the Surakarta Sunanate, which later had the title Paku buwana V. Paku Buwana V, assisted by R.Ng.Yasadipura II, Ki Ng. Ranggasutrasna and Kyai Kasan Besari in the writing of *Serat Centhini* can be said to be spectacular works, so it is not surprising that this work is called an encyclopedia of Javanese Culture. Pigeaud [12] states that this work is filled with encyclopedic descriptions of various branches of science or certain fields of science. Among various kinds of knowledge, *Centhini* Fiber also contains various kinds of food. This work was written in 1814 AD; written in Javanese script, about 4200 pages thick. *Centhini* fibers were printed in Latin letters in 1912 AD by KBG (Koninkelijk Bataviaasch Genootschap van Kunsten en Wetenschappen) vols 5-9. In 1986-1991 the *Centhini* Foundation published 12 volumes of this work translated by Karkana Kamayaya. *Serat Centhini* which contains a variety of contents, namely covering the life of Javanese people, physically and spiritually, philosophy, *kebatinan*, religion, traditions, natural resources, customs, food, beliefs, art to sexuality - this work is what causes the contents of the work to continue to be explored.

Serat Goenandrija is a manuscript written by M. Lagoetama, a farmer from Purwasari, Lawiyan, Surakarta. This manuscript was typed in the old or van Ophysen spelling; there is an explanation that this manuscript is a collection of Th. Pigeaud and received information "Jogjakarta, June 1934". This manuscript is kept at the Sonobudoyo Museum, Yogyakarta.

Serat Wilujengan, *Jumenengan*, *Kraman Mangkunegaran* is a collection of *Reksopustoko*, Mangkunegaran Palace, Surakarta. This text is coded No. 90 MN. Original manuscript without year, written in old or van Ophysen spelling. In 2007 this manuscript was retyped with *Ejaan Yang Disempurnakan*.

Serat Centhini was written about some traditional foods that are still used in various daily needs, including for Javanese traditional ritual ceremonies. Some examples of traditional foods are written in *Serat Centhini* as follows.

1. *Iwak Pitik (Serat Centhini II: 123:24)*
Iwak pitik (chicken meat); In Javanese cuisine, *iwak pitik* is seasoned depending on the importance. How to cultivate; the chicken is cleaned or washed. In Javanese cuisine, you can make *ingkung*, *opor*, fried, *rendang*, *betutu*, steam, and so on. *Iwak Pitik* other than for daily needs, it is also used as an offering tool in ritual ceremonies.
2. *Sekur pulen pethak (Serat Centhini V: 350:20)*
 Fluffier rice is good quality rice; seasoned with coconut oil. How to cultivate; rice is washed, boiled, and given a little coconut oil; stir until the water runs out. The rice is then cooked until cooked. This type of rice is used for daily needs, usually placed in used baskets in courts and communities.
3. *Sekul punar kepyur ura angen (Serat Centhini VI: 357:426)*
Sekul punar ura angen kepyur, namely rice and thick coconut milk; season with pandan leaves, turmeric, bay leaves, and salt. The method of processing is that the rice is washed and half cooked. Satan, salt, turmeric water (turmeric is burned first), bay leaves, and pandan are boiled until boiling. Nasi dikaru (half-cooked) with coconut milk that has been boiled with ground spices. How to serve it; The rice is cooled by being aerated, placed on a tray, decorated and completed with a thinly sliced omelet, fried chili sauce, or dry tempeh, srundeng, peanuts, cucumber, yellow pickle, and fried onions. This type of rice is commonly used by courts and the public; functions as an offering which is usually made of tumpeng and as a complement to thanksgiving or even a clean village traditional ceremony.
4. *Sekul Asahan (Serat Centhini. II: 169:30)*
Sekul asahan; the main ingredient is rice; ordinary dishes such as cooking rice (Javanese: *sega*). The way it is served is placed on a *tampah* (tray) which is equipped with side dishes and *adhem* (not spicy) vegetables. *Sekul asahan* is usually used as offerings. *Sekul asahan* which has been mixed with side dishes and vegetables is then collected in *takir* and distributed to the community.
5. *Sekul Tumpeng Megana (Serat Centhini IV: 321:29)*
Sekul tumpeng megana with the main ingredients of rice, vegetables, anchovies, and young coconut. The spices used are garlic, *kencur*, shrimp paste, chili, and salt. How to make; rice is cooked into white rice, seasoned vegetables, grated young coconut, roasted anchovies (you can add thinly sliced *petai*). The rice is then steamed with vegetables and cooking spices. The way of serving rice in a steamer is reversed and placed on top of the *tampah* which has been coated with banana leaves. The rice is decorated with garnishes in the form of boiled vegetables with herbs (Javanese: *urap*), boiled eggs, *gereh* / fried tofu, fried tempeh, chicken *opor*, *gendar* crackers, cucumber. *Sekul tumpeng megana* is usually placed in *takir* and distributed.
6. *Sekul ulam (Serat Centhini I: 72:34)*
Sekul ulam is made from rice and coconut milk; seasoned with shallots, garlic, coriander, cumin, galangal, roasted turmeric, cloves, salt, coconut oil. How to cultivate; rice cooked with coconut milk, kaffir lime leaves, salt and ground spices, stir-fried. Steam the rice until cooked. How to serve it; served with fried anchovies, soy *sambal bubuk*, fried prawns, beef jerky, omelet, cucumber, and clover. *Sekul ulam* is usually used in community offerings.
7. *Sekul Wuduk (Serat Centhini II: 157:6)*
Sekul wuduk are the main ingredients of rice and coconut milk. How to process rice with coconut milk; seasoned with salt and little fried shallots and white sugar. This food can function either as an offering or not as an offering or a daily meal.

Serat Centhini also written various types of snacks (Javanese: nyamikan) are served in Javanese traditional ceremonies during the colonial period. In the research of Sunjata, et all [13], several snacks wrote in Centhini Fiber are also described as follows.

1. *Ampyang* (*Serat Centhini* II: 157:8; *Serat Centhini* VI: 358:15)
Ampyang is a type of snack made from brown sugar and peanuts.
2. *Apem* (*Serat Centhini* VI: 358:22; *Serat Centhini* VII: 447:1)
Apem is food made from rice flour mixed with sugar or made into a dough; cooked in a frying pan greased with oil and poured spoonful at a time.
3. *Awug-awug* (*Serat Centhini* II: 157-8)
Awug-awug is a food made from glutinous rice flour, grated coconut, salt, and sugar. This dough is divided into two parts and colored with red and white, then put on a baking sheet, steamed until cooked.
4. *Cucur* (*Serat Centhini* II: 358:18)
Cucur is a food made from rice flour, liquid sugar, and coconut milk. The making of this cake is almost the same as *apem*. The dough is cooked in a pan filled with oil and poured over with a spoon.
5. *Carabikang* (*Serat Centhini* I: 32:25)
Carabikang is a food made from rice flour and coconut milk. This dough is put into molds which are usually red and white.
6. *Gandhos* (*Serat Centhini* II: 157-18)
Gandos is a food made from sticky rice that is turned into *jadah* and fried.
7. *Jadah* (*Serat Centhini* II: 129:25; *Serat Centhini* III: 197:34)
Jadah is food made from glutinous rice which is steamed and finely ground.
8. *Jenang Bekatul* (*Serat Centhini* II: 157:7)
Jenang Bekatul in *Serat Centhini* is depicted together with other types of *jenang* as a means of offering *wayang kulit* in *ruwatan* rituals.
9. *Rengginang* (*Serat Centhini* VI: 358:17)
Rengginang is a kind of snack made from white sticky rice. Steam glutinous rice, sprinkle with onion, salt, and shrimp paste. Hot sticky rice is formed round and thin; then dried and fried.

In *Serat Centhini* several types of food are mentioned several times, as in the following example. “*Heh cah wadon ladekna aglis/dhahar sanananira/kang kinen mundur/prapta ambekta rampadan/ dyan tinata liwet lemes akas guring/golong tumpeng megana*” (*Serat Centhini* III: 234: 40). In *Serat Centhini*, the type of *nasi liwet* food, *tumpeng megana* is mentioned several times. *Tumpeng megana* is, for example, served during meals, especially for dishes at the palace when entertaining guests “*Tumpeng megana neng tengah/ pisang kepel balimbing nganan ing/ kinubeng rampadanipun/ ulam mawarna/ brambang bawang timun sumerit/ lalaban kemangi cambah/ sambel uleg pecel pitik*” (*Serat Centhini* III: 255: 32).

In *Serat Centhini* also mentioned some traditional tools such as *jodhang*, **ambegan** or plate (*Serat Centhini* V: 354:22); “*Daharan mawarni-warni/ neng piring Jepun lancaran/ samekta neng jodhang wareng*”; “*mulya amedhalaken ambengan/ rolas ambengan gedhe-gedhe*” (*Serat Centhini* VI: 355:33). *Serat Centhini* also mentions several places (tools) for storing food which are still used by part of Javanese society, namely *panjang ilang* and *takir*.

In a celebration event, for example, at the beginning of the celebration, which is when establishing the *tarub*, it is stated in *Serat Centhini* that two pieces of *ambeg nasi lulut* are provided, namely rice mixed with sticky rice with turmeric and two *ambeg nasi wudhuk*,

namely savory rice with coconut milk, six *ambeng nasi asahan*, twenty pairs of *nasi golong*, market snacks, namely various foods from the market, *dhawet*, *rujak* and its place, chicken *pecel*, *jangan menir*, side dishes or white sheet chicken. *Jenang merah putih*, baro-baro porridge, and white porridge are added with red rice and mixed with Javanese sugar [14]. Some Javanese people today still provide this type of food at certain celebrations.

In *Serat Goenandrija*, there is a story about the King of Kano in Purwacarita, who was given "rice seeds" (Javanese: *wiji pantun*) by Dewa to be planted. Prabu Kano had a patih named Patih Jakapuring, who was none other than his younger brother. He ordered the Jakapuring Patih to plant rice seeds. Jaka Puring is famous for his authority and supernatural powers, so that the genies submit to him. The genies (Javanese: *demit*) who were already afraid of Patih Jaka Puring were told to stay in the corners of the *galengan* (edge) of the rice fields to wait for the rice plants. The ghosts are also willing, but after the rice harvest they ask for wages, that is, offerings that are discarded or not eaten, such as baro-baro *jenang* in the form of various foods and sometimes different. In Goenandrija's fibers, various foods related to the *wiwit* ceremony are mentioned. In the *wiwit* ceremony or rice harvest, the offerings provided are in the form of overlapping vegetables and grilled chickens, market snacks, *sega wuduk ingkung lembaran*, *jenang baro-baro*, *sega kepyar*, *sambel gepeng*, whole eggs, *jenang abang putih*, *dawet* according to the tradition of the ancestors. "*Mula wong wiwit niku beda-beda, enten sing tumpang mawi kuluban lan panggan pitik, lan jajan pasar, enten sing sega wuduk ingkung lembaran, jenang baro-baro, enten sing sega kepyar, sambel gepeng, endog wutuhan, kalih jenang abang putih, enten sing dawet, mekaten miturut kuna-kunanane*" Goenandrija: 25:15).

In *Serat Wilujengan*, *Jumenengan*, *Kraman Mangkunegara* contains various kinds of food as a "symol of respect" to prophets and kings or respected people. The types of food offered are based on their function or importance. Some examples of quotes from *Serat Wilujengan*, *Jumenengan*, *Kraman Mangkunegara* (1-23) are presented as follows.

1. Food to honor Prophet Adam and his wife Siti Kawa (Siti Hawa).
"*Ngaturi dhahar Kanjeng Nabi Adam dan sagarwa Siti Kawa*"; *ambengan sekul pulen saklawhipun, roti mertega keju 1 piring, wedang bubuk mawi powan (susu) 1 cangkir, apem 10 tangkep*".
2. Food to honor Prophet Ibrahim and his wife, Siti Sarah.
"*Ngaturi dhahar Kanjeng Nabi Ibrahim, sagarwa Siti Sarah*"; *apem goreng abrit 10 tangkep, roti mertega keju 1 piring, wedang bubuk powan 1 cangkir, powan tuwin madu*".
3. Food to honor Prophet Muhammad Rasulluloh and his wife, Siti Katijah.
"*Ngaturi dhahar Kanjeng Muhammad Rasulluloh sagarwa Siti Katijah*"; *sekul wuduk ulam lembaran ayam pethak, sarem amper lombok ijo, woh-wohan, roti mertega keju 1 piring, wedang bubuk powan 1 cangkir, kurma, powan tuwin madu*".

In addition, this *serat* also contains the type of food offered to honor the prophets who hold the government (kings), such as Prophet Yusup and Prophet Sulaeman.

1. Food to honor Prophet Yusup and his wife, Siti Zulaika.
"*Ngaturi dhahar Kanjeng Nabi yusup, sagarwa Siti Jaleka*"; *sekul golong duduh pindhang, roti mertega keju 1 piring, wedang bubuk powan, apem*".

2. Food to honor Prophet Sulaeman.
“Ngaturi dhahar Kanjeng Nabi Sulaeman”; *kupat pecel semanggi, roti mertega keju 1 piring, apem, anggur pethak 1 botol*”.
3. In this *Serat*, the daughter of the Prophet Muhammad, Siti Fatimah also received respect.
“Memule Siti Fatimah”, *ketan biru, enten-enten, apem, powan tuwin madu*”.
4. Food to honor the nine saints is also found in this *serat*, for example Sunan Kalijaga.
“Memule Kanjeng Sunan Lepenjaga”; *sekul liwetan, lalapan godhong katu, katul senting, ranti, kudu, gagan-gagan, wali kadhep, sambel plelek*”.

In this *serat* also contains a variety of foods as a symbol of respect for the kings and their ancestors.

1. Food to honor Kanjeng Sunan Pakubuwono I in Surakarta.
“Ngaturi dhahar Kanjeng Sunan Pakubuwono, kapisan ing Surakarta”” *sekul anget lotho, kacang, sekul golong, pecel ayam, jangan menir, pecel wader, apem*”.
2. Food to honor Kanjeng Panembahan Senopati Ngalaga Mataram. As offering for the founder of the Mataram kingdom, the following types of food are provided.
“Ngaturi dhahar kanjeng Panembahan Senopati Ngalaga Mataram”; *sekul par pes-pesan tambra, sekul golong pecel pitik, jangan menir, apem*”.
3. Food to honor Gusti’s Kanjeng Pangeran Adipati Arya Mangkunegara, who was buried in Imogiri.
“Nganturi dhahar Kanjeng Gusti Adipati Arya Mangkunegara, sumare Magiri”; *sekul anget dhendheng age, semur ayam, sop, roti mertega, apem*”.

The types of traditional food and drink recorded in Javanese manuscripts, in general, can be grouped as follows. (1) staple food; *nasi liwet, sega sekul, tumpeng*, porridge, fluffier rice, *sega wuduk punar, sega akas*, fried rice, *sega lemes, sega golong*, and others (2) side dishes: *bubus, cabe, jangan, kuluban, lalab, wangwang, babad, empal; gudheg, jangan aseman, jangan menir, jangan bening, jangan bobor, jangan loncom, jangan lodheh, mangut, opor, pecel pitik, semur, dhendheng, empal, pepesan; sambel lalapan*; Fresh vegetables such as chili sauce, fried chili sauce, *lethok* chili sauce, fresh eggplant, cucumber, basil (3) drinks; *badeg, tuak*, waragang, budur, sajeng, and others; *srebat, beras kencur*, coffee, rock sugar tea, palm sugar ginger drink, chocolate drink; (4) snack; *carah, carana, kiping, lemeng-lemengan, lunggat, lutik, sangan-sangan, apem, kucur, srabi, carabikan, jenang candhil, jenang grendul, jadah, ciriping, ketan kore, lepet, lemper, mendhut*, and others [15].

In the Javanese text of the colonial period, the types of foodstuffs generally originate from domestic foodstuffs and are taken from natural ingredients. The types of animal meat in *Serat Centhini* are *iwak pitik* (chicken meat), beef and buffalo, mutton, tambra fish, gourami. Marsono, et al (1998) identified that in addition to these types of meat or fish, there are also poultry such as pigeons and even rare animals such as deer, *derkuku, kathik* (wren), *mliwis* (grouse), *emprit*. This food ingredient describes a natural atmosphere that is still very natural so that animals are easy to find.

In the text, there is no type of food derived from animals that are prohibited by society, especially Muslims, such as "pigs". Because at the time of writing this text, the Javanese people understood Islam well. However, foreign food elements cannot be separated from the text, for example in *Serat Wilujengan, Jumenengan, Kraman Mangkunegara*, there are several European foreign foods and drinks such as bread butter, cheese butter bread, dates, powdered milk, white wine, and so on.

In the Primbon book (*Lukmanakim Adammakna*) it is mentioned about the types of food for wedding ceremonies, including the following. "sticky rice compote"; in honor of "ancestors. "*Sega adhem-adheman (wajar) lawuhe janganan lan endhog godhogan, tanpa uyah lan liyane*"; white rice, vegetable side dishes and boiled eggs without salt and other spices" to appeal for peace. "*Sega golong lulut, lemek lan tutup endhog dadaran (ngisor lan sandhuwure golong didekeki endhog dadaran*"; Nasi golong, covered with an omelette, begging for the unity of man and God. " "*Jangan padhamara (jangan kangkung nganggo iwak, bumbune brambang, bawang, salam, laos, tumbar, jinten, gula, asem, trasi lan uyah*"; *Jangan padhamara* (water spinach and fish, shallots and garlic spices, salam, galangal, coriander, cumin, sugar, tamarind, shrimp paste and salt beg to live in harmony. "*Tumpeng robyong (endhog godhog sakulite disunduk nganggo sujen, sakdhuwure endhog lan trasi bakaaran banjur brambang, lan dhuwur dhewe lombok. Sundukan ditancepake ing tumpeng. Sakiwa tengene ditancepi sawarnane janganan, nganti tumpeng katon rompyo-rompyo; sarta tumpeng gundhul (tumpeng tanpa lawuhan);); tumpeng robyong* (boiled egg with skin attached), on top of which is grilled shrimp paste and onions on top are chilies, the sticks are attached to the top of the tumpeng on the right and left of the tumpeng with various kinds of vegetables so that the tumpeng looks full and the *tumpeng* is bald, namely tumpeng without side dishes begging for all safet. "*Sega walimah*" (punar rice or savory rice) presented at the time of the marriage consent.

4. CONCLUSION

The expansion of the territory carried out by the Dutch colonialists in the 19th century experienced a lot of resistance from the local elite. The regional expansion that was carried out had an impact on changes in the social order of society, where the king was no longer the only one who was at the highest level in the social order of the community. Besides, the contact between the Bumiputera community and foreign nations has given birth to a mixed culture, hereinafter referred to as *Indis* culture.

The process of strengthening European cultural hegemony towards Indonesian culinary delights in the period 1901-1942 was carried out through various channels, namely through the introduction of foodstuffs and advances in the transportation system, through the introduction of cooking technology, through cooks/cooks. through the establishment of household schools, through writing *kookboek*, and through the establishment of slaughterhouses. The process of strengthening European cultural hegemony cannot be separated from the active role of the Bumiputera people who accept it without leaving elements of their local genius. So that the results obtained in the strengthening process always give rise to a new culture resulting from a mixture of Bumiputera and European cultures.

The form of European cultural influence on Javanese culinary can be recognized through various popular menus that were popular in the Dutch East Indies at that time. The popular menu that developed at that time was not only influenced by Bumiputera, but also had a lot of influence from Europeans. The habit of drinking cold drinks has begun to spread widely among the Bumiputera community. The influence of European culture can also be seen in the change

in the function of some Bumiputera specialties, which from the start to have religious values, to become more commercial.

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